

Supplemental Material

Multi-Source Data Fusion Framework: Assessing Construction Progress

Through Worker Mobility

Accuracy and Coverage of the System

Table S1: Accuracy and Coverage experiment

Time / Metric	Interval Duration (mm:ss)	Duration (mm:ss)	Actual Location (Gateway)	Recorded Location (Gateway)	Category / Result
9:56–9:58	2.00	02:10	53	53	Match
9:58–9:59	1.00	01:00	—	—	No coverage
9:59–10:01	2.00	01:53	53	53	Match
10:01–10:01	0.00	00:12	53	53	Match
10:01–10:02	1.00	00:47	31	31	Match
10:02–10:04	2.00	01:50	31	99	Non-match
10:04–10:05	1.00	00:23	31	31	Match
10:05–10:08	3.00	03:28	99	99	Match
10:08–10:09	1.00	01:00	—	—	No coverage
10:09–10:11	2.00	02:35	99	99	Match
10:11–10:16	5.00	05:11	42	42	Match
10:16–10:21	5.00	04:50	100	100	Match
10:21–10:23	2.00	01:28	111	111	Match
10:23–10:23	0.00	00:23	111	53	Non-match
10:23–10:24	1.00	00:21	111	111	Match
Total Study Window	28.00	27.31			Total time tracked
Total Covered Window		25.31			Excludes No Coverage
Accuracy		23:18 / 28:00			91.3%
Coverage		25:31 / 28:00			90.3%

Weekly presence calculation

Table S2 illustrates this distinction using one week of real data from Floor 1 in Case 1. Worker 153 was absent on Tuesday (< 10 min detected), so the weekly mean is calculated over four days, not five. Worker 159 was present all five days but recorded 0% UP on three of them, and these days are included in the denominator. This approach produces floor-level metrics comparable across floors, weeks, and cases.

Table S2: Weekly presence calculation of Floor 1 (Case 1)

Week	Worker	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Days	Weekly Mean
Week of 15 Apr	153	0.0%	absent	0.0%	13.2%	0.0%	4	3.3%
Week of 15 Apr	159	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	11.4%	11.2%	5	4.5%
Week of 15 Apr	Team Average							3.9%

Visual Analytics through 360 Degree Videos:

The percentage represents the estimate of work completed, red box represents the presence of a workshop area, blue box represents presence of material piles, yellow box shows the presence of a meeting area and green box represents entry/exit points. X represents an area where videos could not be collected on that week (e.g. because the floor had not yet started or for safety reasons). Data collection on each floor started when the management informed the researchers that work had started on that floor. There were 12 instances of missing video data in ongoing locations. On some data collection days, not all floors were available for researchers for safety reasons, which explains this missing data.

As an example, the period from May 6th to May 17th is described in detail. The progress advanced from 50 to 60% on the first floor. The progress on second floor was 70% on the first week but data was unavailable during the second week because of safety restrictions. There were workshops and material storage areas on both floors. It was not possible to enter or exit the site from the 1st floor on

May 6th but a new exit was opened by May 17th. In later videos, entry and exit events could not be reliably detected. Initially, workers used a single known path through the first floor, where gateways captured their arrival and departure. However, once internal elevators became available, workers could enter and exit the building at multiple first-floor locations, not all of which were covered by IPS gateways. It can be seen from the table that the locations of temporary spaces supporting sprinkler work were changing a lot during construction.

Figure S1. Excel log of Visual Analytics from weekly videos

Log of observations - Visual Analytics								
Sprinkler Work								
Date	Floor 1	Floor 2	Floor 3	Floor 4	Floor 5	Floor 6	Floor 7	Floor 8
21/03/2024	30 %	X	20 %	X	X	X	X	X
28/03/2024	X	X	40 %	X	X	X	X	X
04/04/2024	30 %	70 %	50 %	5 %	X	X	X	X
12/04/2024	X	70 %	X	X	X	X	X	X
18/04/2024	30 %	70 %	60 %	5 %	0 %	0 %	X	X
26/04/2024	X	70 %	70 %	5 %	10 %	0 %	X	X
06/05/2024	50 %	70 %	80 %	5 %	25 %	0 %	X	X
17/05/2024	60 %	X	80 %	15 %	X	0 %	0 %	X
23/05/2024	70 %	80 %	90 %	15 %	40 %	0 %	X	X
31/05/2024	80 %	80 %	90 %	15 %	60 %	0 %	0 %	X
06/06/2024	80 %	80 %	90 %	15 %	70 %	0 %	0 %	X
13/06/2024	90 %	90 %	90 %	15 %	80 %	X	0 %	X
20/06/2024	90 %	90 %	90 %	15 %	90 %	0 %	10 %	90 %
27/06/2024	90 %	100 %	90 %	15 %	100 %	0 %	20 %	X
18/07/2024	90 %	100 %	100 %	40 %	100 %	20 %	30 %	X
25/07/2024	90 %	100 %	100 %	50 %	100 %	40 %	40 %	X
31/07/2025	90 %	100 %	100 %	60 %	100 %	60 %	60 %	X
08/08/2024	100 %	100 %	100 %	70 %	100 %	80 %	70 %	X
15/08/2024	100 %	100 %	100 %	80 %	100 %	X	80 %	X
26/08/2024	100 %	100 %	100 %	90 %	100 %	100 %	90 %	100 %

Residual Diagnostics:

Figure S2: Residual Diagnostics

